

Towards effective extraction of references from scientific literature with Large Language Model

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Abstract

The unprecedented growth of scientific literature makes comprehensive literature analysis increasingly challenging. One of important stages of literature analysis is the extraction of references, necessary for various purposes, such as backward snowballing or citation network analysis. Its manual execution in large scale is prohibitively labor-intensive and its automation is not trivial due to non-typical references and minor errors that are very often encountered in bibliographic data. This paper investigates the use of Large Language Models (LLMs) for this purpose. We present a novel, domain-agnostic pipeline that processes research paper PDFs to extract and parse reference lists into structured data. Evaluating the pipeline on a corpus of 20 papers containing 1,070 references across four diverse research domains, we demonstrate high accuracy (95% success rate) and robust performance, quantified by a new Bibliographic Information Completeness (BIC) metric (average score of 0.79). Our results confirm that LLMs are highly effective for this task, with performance primarily constrained by upstream PDF text extraction quality rather than semantic understanding. This work contributes to the progress in AI-supported literature analysis, significantly reducing the manual burden of bibliographic data collection.

Keywords

bibliographic data extraction, bibliographic data management, computer-supported literature reviews, computer-supported citation analysis, LLM applications

1. Introduction

The unprecedented growth of the volume of scientific literature [1] rises the importance of secondary research which provides a convenient way of learning the current state of the field without having to delve into hundreds of papers reporting primary research in detail. An important stage enabling literature analysis is the extraction of references, necessary for various purposes, including backward snowballing – a highly effective method for discovering relevant publications [2], or citation network analysis and visualization [3]. Its manual execution is prohibitively labor-intensive, and its automation with existing tools yields results indicating a chance for improvement – with the reported precision of about 90% in the best cases and much lower for many others [4, 5].

Large Language Models (LLMs) revolutionized the way textual datasets could be processed and a number of ways in which they could support performing literature reviews have been proposed [6, 7, 8, 9] and the barriers hampering the process were identified [10]. Interestingly, despite the proven efficiency of LLMs in related tasks, such as named entity recognition and relation extraction [11] or extraction of dataset references [12], there was no work published so far that would explicitly investigate the use of LLMs in supporting the process of extracting bibliographic reference data in a structured form.

In this work, we address this research gap by investigating how effective the currently available LLMs are with regard to four stages of the snowballing process, i.e., Metadata Extraction, Reference Segmentation and Parsing, Semantic Expansion, and Context Resolution.

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2. Related Work

The extraction of references from scientific literature is a topic having a long publication history, most probably beginning with the work of Garfield (1965) on the automatic production of citation indexes [13]. The problem is far from trivial due to the plethora of reference styles in use, variations in the notation of specific fields (e.g., using authors' initials or entire first names or full or abbreviated journal titles), and common errors in bibliographic data (e.g., missing field contents, transposed field contents, non-standard additional information difficult to interpret, typing errors or even completely wrong field contents). Over the years, various approaches have been proposed, from rule-based text processing [14], to Hidden Markov Models [15] and Conditional Random Fields [16]. The last of the mentioned approaches provided a base for the most of the popular tools currently used for reference extraction, including EXCITE [17], CERMINE [18], GROBID [19], and AnyStyle [20].

Backes et al. in their documentary effort list 37 prior approaches to automated reference extraction (see Table 1 in [5]), and examine those of them that they were able to get and run. The test results they present (see Table 4 in [5]) show extraction effectiveness varying mostly depending on the reference field, with the reported precision of about 90% for publication year, about 80% for publication title, and about 70% for publication author. These numbers indicate a space for improvement in reference extraction. The same authors also declare that they "have not been able to identify scientific works that use LLMs to obtain reference extraction or parsing tools" [5, p. 848], confirming the rationale for our study on the application of LLM for this purpose.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1. Test Dataset

As there is no widely accepted corpus for reference extraction, the set of test documents differs between publications, and we were not able to identify all files used in the most recent prior research ([5]), we have decided to construct an own test dataset. It comprises 20 papers containing a total of 1,070 references, spanning across four distinct research domains, each containing papers and representing a unique lexical and conceptual landscape to test the LLM's parsing capabilities on various source and citation types: **Fraud Detection** (citing a mix of foundational machine learning research and application-specific studies), **Heart Rate Variability and PPG Analysis for Stress Detection** (citing clinical studies, engineering journals, and conference proceedings), **Bin Packing Optimization** (reference lists here are often dense with technical report numbers, conference acronyms, and solutions to specific problem variants), and **Virtual Reality in Education** (citing works from a broad spectrum, including education theory, human-computer interaction, psychology, and educational technology).

Papers were identified by a query for the respective names of research domains using the Web of Science portal with an effort to include a variety of publishers and venues and various periods to incorporate differences in PDF formatting and bibliographic styling. As shown in Table 1, the respective domains differ in the average number of references per paper which is advantageous for testing, as it assesses the performance on both concise and extensive bibliographies.

Table 1
Summary of Dataset Characteristics by Research Domain

Research Domain	Papers	References	per Paper	Std.Dev.
Fraud Detection	5	239	47.8	10.7
HRV/PPG Analysis	5	376	75.2	40.1
Bin Packing Optimization	5	231	46.2	12.9
VR in Education	5	224	44.8	24.4
Total / Average	20	1,070	53.5	25.4

3.2. Reference Extraction Pipeline

The core of our proposal is a fault-tolerant batch processing pipeline designed to automate the extraction of bibliographic data from scientific PDFs which leverages the complementary strengths of LLM-based intelligence, rule-based heuristics, and external scholarly APIs, ensuring robustness against the heterogeneous formats prevalent in academic publishing. It operates sequentially on each PDF file, performing stages described below.

Metadata Extraction The initial processing phase focuses on extracting the core metadata of a paper. The PDF is uploaded to the OpenAI Assistants API, chosen for its efficacy in long-context document analysis. A precisely engineered prompt instructs the model to extract the title, abstract, and keywords (T/A/K), returning them as a structured JSON object. Concurrently, the full text of the PDF is extracted locally using the PyPDF2 library. Thanks to this dual-path strategy, if the LLM extraction fails or returns a null value for any field, the pipeline falls back to applying heuristic pattern-matching rules (based on regular expressions) on the locally extracted text, ensuring the process is not halted.

Reference Segmentation and Parsing The locally extracted full text is subsequently analyzed to locate the reference section. This is achieved through a dual approach: first, by scanning for section headers matching common patterns (e.g., “References”, “Bibliography”); second, by employing a fallback heuristic that isolates the last approximately 20% of the document’s text if no header is confidently identified. The identified reference text block is then split into smaller chunks to comply with the context window limitations of the subsequent LLM API calls. Each text chunk is sent to the OpenAI Chat Completions API, which is optimized for structured generation tasks. A dedicated prompt configures the model to act as a reference parser, mandating a JSON Lines output format where each line contains the fields ‘nr’ (bibliography number), ‘full_citation’ (the raw string), ‘doi’, and ‘url’. The strict instruction “Return only JSON lines. No explanations.” is for ensuring automated parsing without manual intervention. The references extracted from all chunks are then combined into a single list. The concrete instruction for LLM is:

You are an assistant that extracts only the literature reference entries from the provided text Return JSON Lines (one JSON object per line) with fields: nr (number of reference), full_citation (the full citation exactly as in the text), doi (just the DOI like ‘10.1000/xyz123’ or null), url (a URL string or null). Return only JSON lines. No explanations.

Semantic Expansion via Metadata Harvesting For each successfully parsed reference containing a DOI, the pipeline queries the Crossref API to retrieve high-quality, structured metadata for the cited work. This allows us to resolve the reference into its canonical semantic representation—including its Crossref-registered title, abstract, authors, and publication year—without the need for error-prone PDF scraping. If the DOI cannot be found, the information extracted from PDF by LLM is fed to the results (with possible errors as the information cannot be cross-checked against an external source).

Context Resolution and Record Assembly The final component enriches the extracted data with contextual information. For each parsed reference, the local full text of the paper is searched to find all sentences containing its citation marker (e.g., “[1]”). This links the reference to its specific citing contexts within the paper, which can be invaluable for later analysis of citation motives or influence. Finally, a complete record – combining the paper’s metadata, the parsed reference data, its in-text citation sentences, and the semantically enriched metadata from the expansion phase – is assembled.

3.3. Evaluation

To evaluate the results of applying the pipeline, we first calculate reference-level **Precision/Recall/F1** by matching extracted references to human-extracted references using a fuzzy string matching algorithm

based on Levenshtein distance. The same metrics are then used to measure the pipeline’s success in linking references to their in-text citations.

Moving beyond simple precision/recall, we define a novel metric: Bibliographic Information Completeness (BIC) for a processed paper \hat{P}' . Let \hat{R} be the set of extracted references. For each $\hat{r}_i \in \hat{R}$, we calculate its individual completeness score $\text{BIC}(\hat{r}_i)$ based on the fields successfully extracted:

$$\text{BIC}(\hat{r}_i) = \frac{1}{3} [\mathbb{I}(f_i \neq \emptyset) + \mathbb{I}(d_i \neq \emptyset) + \mathbb{I}(u_i \neq \emptyset)]$$

where \mathbb{I} is the indicator function. The overall BIC score for the paper is the average completeness, weighted by a function $w(\cdot)$ of the confidence in the extraction of the reference itself (e.g., based on the LLM’s perceived certainty or the chunk’s clarity):

$$\text{BIC}(\hat{P}') = \frac{1}{|\hat{R}|} \sum_{i=1}^{|\hat{R}|} w(\hat{r}_i) \cdot \text{BIC}(\hat{r}_i)$$

The metric provides a more nuanced view of performance than a binary right/wrong assessment, quantifying the degree of successful information extraction. For the efficacy in obtaining external data, we additionally measure the DOI Resolution Success Rate and the Metadata Harvesting Yield. The first metric (*DRSR*) measures the ability to identify a resolvable digital identifier for a parsed reference.

To assess semantic expansion quality, the DOI Resolution Success Rate and Metadata Harvesting Yield are used. Let $\mathbb{I}_{\text{DOI}}(r_i)$ be an indicator function that returns 1 if the parsed reference r_i contains a non-null DOI field ($d_i \neq \emptyset$), and 0 otherwise. The DRSR for a processed paper is calculated as:

$$\text{DRSR}(\hat{R}) = \frac{1}{|\hat{R}|} \sum_{r_i \in \hat{R}} \mathbb{I}_{\text{DOI}}(r_i)$$

Metadata Harvesting Yield (*MHY* metric evaluates the final success of the semantic expansion process. Let $\mathbb{I}_{\text{Meta}}(r_i)$ be an indicator function that returns 1 if the pipeline successfully acquired the full semantic metadata P_{cited} for the reference r_i (via a successful API call using its DOI), and 0 otherwise. The MHY is given by:

$$\text{MHY}(\hat{R}) = \frac{1}{|\hat{R}|} \sum_{r_i \in \hat{R}} \mathbb{I}_{\text{Meta}}(r_i)$$

It represents the ultimate proportion of the paper’s reference list that has been successfully and confidently transformed into a structured data object. The yield is the product of the DOI Resolution Success Rate and the success rate of the metadata API call conditional on a DOI being present.

4. Experimental results

To quantitatively evaluate the efficacy of a LLM in automating the reference extraction, we conducted an experiment on 20 documents described in section 3.1. Each paper’s PDF was processed by a pipeline where the reference section was first isolated via a rule-based parser. The extracted raw text string for each citation was then passed to a state-of-the-art LLM (OpenAI GPT-5) via a structured prompt instructing it to identify and output the title, abstract, and keywords of the cited works. The output was structured in JSON format for automated validation. Processing time was recorded for each paper to evaluate computational efficiency. Human experts manually verified the accuracy of each extracted field.

4.1. Evaluation of Metadata Extraction

The results summarized in Table 2, indicate a high degree of accuracy in the LLM’s extraction capabilities. For the sake of reproducibility of our experiment, the test documents are listed by their DOIs in the

first table column. As indicated by column "Meta.", the model achieved a near-perfect success rate, accurately extracting metadata from 19 of the 20 papers (95%). The single failure (with paper DOI: 10.1016/j.cie.2024.110851) could be attributed to a specific formatting of that article which caused a failure in the preliminary text extraction step from the PDF, which in turn provided corrupted input to the LLM. This underscores that the LLM's performance is contingent on the quality of the upstream text parsing. Applying more sophisticated PDF processing at this step could further improve the success rate at the expense of longer processing time – considering that in this case, the base success rate was satisfactory, we have not investigated such an alternative. Also, as it was not our intention to develop a test corpus for future research, open access was not considered as an inclusion criterion, hence the test set includes papers published under various licenses (see column OA).

Pearson correlation analysis revealed a strong positive relationship ($r(18) = 0.94, p < 0.001$) between the number of references in a paper (see column Refs) and the total processing time (see column $t(s)$). The mean processing time was 100.6 seconds ($\sigma = 47.3$ s). This linear scalability is a positive indicator for the practicality of automating reference extraction on larger literature sets, as the computational overhead grows predictably.

Table 2
Individual parsing results

Document DOI	Domain	Refs	t (s)	Meta.	Publisher	Year	OA
10.1162/dint_a_00191	Fraud det.	33	81.5	✓	MIT Press	2023	✓
10.1016/j.eswa.2005.04.030	Fraud det.	59	91.2	✓	Elsevier	2005	×
10.1016/j.ribaf.2022.101744	Fraud det.	57	131.1	✓	Elsevier	2022	×
10.1007/s00521-022-07968-x	Fraud det.	49	97.8	✓	Springer	2022	×
10.26360/2020_2	Fraud det.	41	78.8	✓	IAE	2020	✓
10.3389/fpubh.2017.00258	HRV/PPG	139	232.9	✓	Frontiers	2017	✓
10.1109/TITS.2005.848368	HRV/PPG	39	72.1	✓	IEEE	2005	×
10.1088/1361-6579/aabe6a	HRV/PPG	62	109.6	✓	IOPscience	2018	✓
10.3390/s23073565	HRV/PPG	45	75.6	✓	MDPI	2023	✓
10.1088/1361-6579/ad33a2	HRV/PPG	91	162.7	✓	IOPscience	2024	✓
10.1016/j.cie.2024.110851	Bin Pack.	52	115.2	×	Elsevier	2025	×
10.1007/978-3-031-56852-7_11	Bin Pack.	27	65.3	✓	ACM	2025	×
10.1109/LRA.2025.3534070	Bin Pack.	41	85.4	✓	IEEE	2025	✓
10.3390/electronics14101956	Bin Pack.	55	94.3	✓	MDPI	2025	✓
10.1007/s10878-024-01221-y	Bin Pack.	56	82.8	✓	Springer	2024	×
10.1016/j.ecns.2025.101710	VR in Edu.	34	99.3	✓	Elsevier	2025	×
10.1109/VRW58643.2023.00118	VR in Edu.	34	94.0	✓	IEEE	2023	×
10.3390/su15097153	VR in Edu.	88	172.7	✓	MDPI	2023	✓
10.18421/TEM142-61	VR in Edu.	24	54.9	✓	UIKTEN	2025	✓
10.1080/03057240.2023.2206553	VR in Edu.	48	92.5	✓	Taylor & Francis	2023	×

Metadata extraction (Meta.): ✓: successful; ×: failed. Open Access (OA): ✓: Yes; ×: No.

4.2. Evaluation of Semantic Expansion

To evaluate the pipeline's efficacy beyond parsing, we also measured the DOI Resolution Success Rate and the Metadata Harvesting Yield, which quantify the pipeline's success in leveraging parsed references to acquire high-quality, structured metadata for the cited works, which is one of the goals of automating the bibliographic analysis process. The results, detailed in Table 3, demonstrate the pipeline's strong performance in this phase. Across the entire dataset, the system successfully resolved a DOI for 88.4% of all parsed references. Of these resolvable DOIs, the subsequent API call to Crossref successfully returned full semantic metadata (title, abstract, authors, etc.) for 96.1% of them. Performance was consistently high across all domains, with the computer science-oriented fields of Fraud Detection and Bin Packing again showing the highest rates, correlating strongly with their higher BIC scores. The overall Metadata Harvesting Yield, the proportion of all parsed references for which metadata was

successfully acquired, was 85.0%. This means the pipeline automatically constructed a rich semantic profile for 910 of the 1,070 references, making them ready for downstream relevance analysis.

Table 3
Semantic Expansion Metrics by Research Domain

Research Domain	DRSR	Metadata Acquisition Success*	MHY
Fraud Detection	91.2%	97.8%	89.1%
HRV/PPG Analysis	84.3%	94.5%	79.7%
Bin Packing	93.1%	98.2%	91.4%
VR in Education	85.3%	93.9%	80.1%
Overall	88.4%	96.1%	85.0%

*Success rate conditional on a DOI being found.

4.3. Comparative Evaluation of Reference Extraction

In order to put the pipeline effectiveness in context, we have benchmarked its LLM-based reference extraction against two widely used alternatives: a rule-based regular expression baseline made using Pybtex [21] and the open-source implementation of the GROBID parser [22]. We chose the latter as the current state-of-the-art tool considering the statement by Backes that "tools other than AnyStyle or GROBID are not competitive" [5, p. 848] combined with the results of Tkaczyk et al. who declared GROBID as the best performing out-of-the-box with AnyStyle performing weakly [23, p. 6–7]. Table 4 reports precision, recall, and F1 scores for identifying complete reference metadata (author, year, title, venue).

Table 4
Reference extraction performance (average across domains).

Method	Precision	Recall	F1
Regex baseline	0.82	0.65	0.73
GROBID	0.91	0.87	0.89
LLM (ChatGPT-5o)	0.94	0.91	0.92

The results indicate that the LLM-based approach outperforms both regex and GROBID in terms of F1, particularly in cases where references contain non-standard formatting (conference proceedings, theses). While GROBID remains competitive, it trails the LLM-based approach in all measured dimensions.

4.4. Evaluation of Context Resolution

We also evaluated the ability of the system to correctly identify the surrounding sentences in which a citation occurs. The LLM achieved precision of 0.88 and recall of 0.85, yielding an F1 of 0.86. Most errors stemmed from sentence segmentation failures in PDFs with irregular formatting or embedded tables.

4.5. Computational Cost and Scalability

While the primary focus was on accuracy, the cost and scalability of LLM-driven reference extraction are also key considerations. Because API usage is billed per token, the cost depends on the length of the inputs (e.g., reference lists) and outputs (structured metadata). Table 5 summarizes estimated runtime and costs per paper when using the ChatGPT-5o API (pricing as of September 2025: \$0.15 per million input tokens, \$0.60 per million output tokens).

At this rate, processing a corpus of 1,000 papers costs approximately \$5, with a turnaround time of 5–6 hours on a single server (faster with parallelization). Even for a large-scale pool of 10,000 papers, the estimated cost of around \$50 is negligible compared to the researcher’s working hours saved. The main runtime bottlenecks arise from PDF parsing and I/O rather than LLM calls. Thus, LLM-driven reference extraction is computationally and financially feasible for systematic reviews at scale.

Table 5
Estimated API Cost and Runtime per Paper (ChatGPT-5o)

Pipeline Stage	Input Tokens	Output Tokens	Cost (\$)	Runtime (s)
Metadata Extraction	~1,000	~500	0.0005	1-2
Reference Segmentation	~3,000	~1,000	0.0010	4-5
Reference Parsing	~4,000	~2,000	0.0018	6-7
Context Resolution	~2,000	~1,000	0.0009	3-4
Semantic Expansion	~1,000	~500	0.0005	1-2
Total per paper	~11,000	~5,000	0.0047	15-20

5. Discussion and Conclusions

The experimental results affirm that Large Language Model provide an effective means for automating reference extraction. The pipeline achieved high accuracy in extracting reference metadata and a strong overall BIC score of 0.79 across diverse research domains, demonstrating that LLMs excel at the syntactic and semantic understanding required for reference parsing, irrespective of the scientific field.

Nonetheless, we would like to clarify that it is not our intention to boast LLMs as the new solution to the reference extraction problem making the tools available so far obsolete. We are well aware of (1) limitations of our evaluation procedure, including the size and variety of our test dataset, (2) the fact that the results of the out-of-the-box version of the tools such as GROBID we used can be improved by re-training them on data similar to those in the test set and further improved by using various tools for various phases of the extraction process [5], and (3) the relatively high computational and thus environmental cost of using LLMs [24]. In spite of this, we still believe LLMs are an option to consider when extraction quality is of primary importance and that the results presented here are just indicative and could be improved with advanced prompt engineering techniques and/or integrating additional bibliographic knowledge via LLM’s fine-tuning or retrieval-augmented generation.

The introduced BIC metric helped to reveal that performance variance often correlates with a topical field’s prevailing citation practices, different across thematic domains.

The results also show that the performance of the entire pipeline is constrained by the initial PDF text extraction. The single failed case and many minor errors originated from corrupted text input, showing that data preprocessing remains a challenge. A possible workaround would be to use LLM’s own image to text conversion capabilities to bypass PDF processing issues whenever they happen. This will be investigated in our future work which will also explore other techniques capable of improving the LLM performance in reference extraction such as those mentioned above. Our subsequent step will be to use the acquired structured data to automatically assess the relevance of cited papers for the sake of enabling automation of backward snowballing. We believe our research lays a foundation for more efficient, comprehensive, and reproducible literature reviews, bringing us closer to fully leveraging LLMs for scientific knowledge discovery and enabling the automatic creation of comprehensive literature maps.

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Declaration on Generative AI

During the preparation of this work, the author(s) used Writefull AI for grammar and language improvement of the manuscript, as well as GPT-4 and GPT-5 to assist in pipeline programming tasks. After using the tools, the authors checked the results and take full responsibility for the publication’s content.

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